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INFLUENCE OF BREAKAGES OF CABLE GROUPS ON STRENGTH OF RUBBER-CABLE TRACTIVE-TRANSPORTING ELEMENT

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ВПЛИВ РОЗРИВІВ ГРУП ТРОСІВ НА МІЦНІСТЬ ГУМОТРОСОВОГО ТЯГОВО-ТРАНСПОРТУВАЛЬНОГО ОРГАНА

Purpose. Development and justification of a method of analytical determination of a stress-strain state of a flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element with breakages of continuity of cable groups in different cross-sections.

Methodology of research is in development of a mathematical model of interaction of tractive-transporting element parts considering breakages of groups of random cables, construction of analytical solutions for determining dependencies of force distribution between cables and shear stresses in an elastic shell of a tractive-transporting element with random locations of breakages of cable groups in different cross-sections.

Findings. A model of a flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element with random locations of breakages of cable groups in different cross-sections is developed. Expressions that allow determining a stress-strain state of a flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element of a hoisting and transporting machine with random locations of breakages of cable groups in different cross-sections are obtained analytically in a closed form. Strength conditions are formulated.

Scientific novelty is in establishment of dependencies of interaction of disturbance fields of a stress-strain state of a rubber-cable tractive-transporting element with breakages of continuity of random cable groups in different cross-sections. It is established that disturbance fields caused by breakages of adjacent cables overlap when the breakages are located in one cross-section and there are less than three whole cables located between the broken cables. Disturbance fields also overlap when the same cable or the adjacent cable is broken in both cross-sections and the distance between cross-sections of breakage does not exceed the value, which depends on the design of a flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element and mechanical properties of its components.

Practical significance. The obtained algorithms and strength conditions allow determining a stress-strain state and preventing the breakage of the entire flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element with breakages of cable groups in different cross-sections. These cross-sections can be: cross-section of the edge of a butt joint, where cables have breakages of continuity; cross-section, which includes the edge of an area of partial restoration of a tractive ability of the element, lost due to breakage of a cable; cross-section of cable or cable group breakage during operation. A possibility of establishing a stress-strain state and the strength conditions of a tractive-transporting element under such conditions allows reasonable determination of a possibility of its further operation in a hoisting and transporting machine.

Keywords: *hoisting and transporting machine, flat rubber-cable tractive-transporting element, mathematical model, boundary conditions, stress-strain state, cable base continuity breakage, calculation method, strength conditions.*

Introduction. Lifting and transporting equipment takes a special place in industrial production. The feature is that it provides transportation of materials between technological operations and is associated with increased emergency risk. At the same time, breakage of a reinforcement system of tractive-transporting elements (belts, ropes) of lifting and transporting machines is especially dangerous. Such breakage is realized due to local loss of strength by a specific cable (which carries maximum load), and cable breakage leads to loss of strength and breakage of other cables and, ultimately, to the breakage of a tractive-transporting element of the machine as a whole. Restoration of tractive-transporting elements is more cost-effective than their replacement. Restoration of the belt reinforcement system is performed by replacing parts of cables [1]. As a result, there can be several breakages of continuity of cables (ropes) in a belt. Since a breakage of even one cable leads to a decrease in tractive capacity of a belt and a possibility of emergency breakage, determination of its tractive capacity is an *urgent scientific and technical problem*.

State of issue and research problem statement. The influence of cable breakages on strength of rubber-cable belts and ropes has been considered by many scientists [2–5]. The case of determining a stress-strain state of a belt with breakages of continuity of groups of cables in different cross-sections of the belt was not considered and the method of its determination has not been developed. The article aims to develop such a method.

The relative position of several breakages of cables affects the maximum loading forces of cables and shear stress of rubber among them, provided that the zones of stress disturbances caused by breakages overlap. The overlapping of disturbance zones depends on distances between breakages, both in belt (rope) length and in width, and on the number of cables in a belt (rope). There are different types of belts that are used in the industry. This requires determining the stress-strain state in a general form.

Paper results. Consider the following case for a rope of limited length. Rope cables are broken in two cross-sections: $x = 0$, $x = L$. These cross-sections divide the rope into three parts. Assign numbers 1-3 to the parts. Forms of solutions for equilibrium equations of cables have the same forms for each of these parts. Values in the solutions [3] are denoted by an additional index ρ . Its value is equal to the part number.

$$p_{i,\rho} = E F \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \left(A_{m,\rho} e^{\beta_m x} - B_{m,\rho} e^{-\beta_m x} \right) \beta_m \cos(\mu_m (i - 0,5)) + a_\rho, \quad (1)$$

$$u_{i,\rho} = \sum_{m=1}^{M-1} \left(A_{m,\rho} e^{\beta_m x} + B_{m,\rho} e^{-\beta_m x} \right) \cos(\mu_m (i - 0,5)) + \frac{a_\rho x}{E F} + b_\rho, \quad (2)$$

where u , p are axial displacement and internal cable loading; i is cable number in a rope; $A_{m,\rho}$, $B_{m,\rho}$, a_ρ , b_ρ are unknown coefficients; E , F are reduced modulus of elasticity and a cross-section area of a rope cable; G is shear modulus of a shell material; k_G is coefficient of influence of shape of elastic material layer on its rigidity;